

CHEMICAL SCIENCES

SULFUR-, PHOSPHORUS-CONTAINING ETHERS AND STUDY OF THEIR TRIBIOLOGICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Synthesized esters of xanthogen, dithiophosphoric, and tricarbonic acids. The structure of the obtained compounds was confirmed by elemental analysis data from IR and PMR spectroscopy. Tests were carried out in MS-20 oil, their high extreme pressure efficiency was shown. Studies of the lubricating properties of the synthesized esters were carried out on a four-ball friction machine (ChShM-1) in accordance with GOST 9490-75. Comparative studies of the synthesized compounds in the mineral oil MS-20 were carried out, and the optimal concentrations of the resulting compounds were selected. Replacing the alkyl radical with a phenyl radical leads to a decrease in the extreme pressure efficiency of these compounds. Benzoyloxymethyl esters of TTC, DTP and KG acids are more thermally stable compared to acetoxymethyl esters. The resulting compounds have high anti-wear, extreme pressure properties and high thermal stability, which can be used to create effective lubricating oils.

Keywords: Synthesis, esters, xanthates, dithiophosphates, trithiocarbonates, additives, lubricating oils, benzoyl chloride.

Introduction

Increasing the operational reliability and durability of machines and mechanisms is of great importance for the technical and economic potential of every developed country. As a result of the insufficient durability of machines and mechanisms, the rate of technical progress decreases and the costs of repair maintenance of the machine fleet increase.

Analysis of the literature review on the synthesis and use of compounds as extreme pressure additives shows that sulfur-containing compounds occupy a special place, which have found use in lubricating oils as additives. Their effectiveness depends on many factors, the main one of which is the composition and structure of the compounds used. The vast majority of extreme pressure additives used and recommended for use include sulfur, nitrogen, phosphorus and chlorine.

As is known, esters of dithiophosphoric (DTF), xanthogenic (KG), and trithiocarboxylic (TTK) acids are used in various sectors of the national economy. It is known that they are used as stabilizers, rubbers and polyolefins bactericides and fungicides [1-5] plasticizers polyphenyl chloride[6-7].. flotation agents, as well as additives for lubricants. The above compounds are of particular interest as extreme pressure additives for lubricating oils. Extreme pressure additives are added to oils to prevent reduction of wear and friction of metal

surfaces of joints[8-9]. The role of extreme pressure additives for oils, acting chemically, is that, by forming compounds with reduced shear resistance on the metal surface, they ensure easy destruction of the bonds, and thus prevent plastic hardening of the surface layers, i.e. create a positive shear stress gradient. As additives to lubricating oils, derivatives of xanthogen (KG), O, O-dialkyldithiophosphoric [10-13], trithiocarboxylic acids (TTK) are widely used in industry.

In the search for effective additives for lubricating oils, it is of interest to synthesize and study new representatives of these classes of compounds containing various polar groups.

The purpose of this article is to obtain effective additives for lubricating oils based on benzoyloxymethyl esters of TTK, KG, DTF acids containing an aromatic ring and an ester group in the molecule. The derivatives of the above acids we obtained, their properties and applications are not described in the literature.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

Synthesis of esters of xanthogen and trithiocarbonic acids

By reacting benzoyloxymethyl chloride with alkali metal xanthates in benzene at 50-60°C, a series of new benzoyloxymethyl esters of xanthogenic acids was synthesized with a yield of 85–88% (14).

R-C₂H₅, i C₃H₇, C₄H₉

We obtained similar compounds by counter synthesis by reacting hydroxymethyl esters of xanthogenic acids with benzoyl chloride of carboxylic acids.

R-C₂H₅, i C₃H₇, C₄H₉

The reaction involving hydroxymethyl esters of KG acids with benzoyl chloride of carboxylic acids was carried out at 35-40°C for 2 hours in the presence of a catalyst - triethylamine. The yield was 85%.

Identification of compounds was carried out by recording infrared absorption spectra on a SPECORD-75

IR IR spectrophotometer, manufactured by Karl-Zeiss (GDR) using KBr, NaCl and LiF prisms in the region 4000-400 cm⁻¹. In the IR spectrum of S-benzoyloxymethyl ester of isopropyl-xanthogenic acid, an intense absorption band is detected at 1720 cm⁻¹, corresponding to vibrations of the C=O group. Characteristic bands are also observed with a frequency at 1100 cm⁻¹ and 650 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the C=S and C-S groups, the phenyl group appears at 1600 cm⁻¹.

To expand the arsenal of additives for lubricating oils that have high anti-wear and extreme pressure activity, benzoyloxymethyl ester of butyl trithiocarbonic acid was synthesized. The interaction of benzoyloxymethyl chloride with sodium butyl trithiocarbonate at 65-70°C was carried out by subsequent isolation of the target product[15].

Pic.1. IR and PRM spectra of benzoyloxymethylester of isopropylxanthogenic acid

The starting benzoyloxymethyl chloride is obtained by reacting benzoyl chloride with paraform in the presence of ZnCl₂.

In the IR spectra of this compound, absorption bands are observed in the region of 1055-1058 cm⁻¹, corresponding to the S-C(S)-S group. An intense absorption band in the region of 1750 cm⁻¹ characterizes the C=O group, the C-O-O bond in the indicated ether is characterized by an intense absorption band in the region of 1150-1060 cm⁻¹. The intense absorption band

with a frequency of 1610 cm⁻¹ belongs to the aromatic ring.

Benzoyloxymethyl esters of DTP acids were obtained by reacting benzoic acid chloromethyl ester with sodium O,O-dialkyl dithiophosphate for 7-8 hours at a temperature of 80-90°C. The yield of the target product is 85%.

R-i C₃H₇, C₅H₁₁

The original chloromethyl ester of benzoic acid was obtained by reacting benzoyl chloride with paraform according to a known method.

These compounds were obtained by an alternative method by reacting hydroxymethyl esters of dithiophosphoric acids with benzoic acid chloride. The identity of the compounds obtained by both methods was proven by studying their elemental composition, as well as IR and PMR spectra.

In the IR spectrum of benzyloxymethyl ester of OO-diisopropyl dithiophosphoric acid, an intense absorption band at 1740 cm^{-1} corresponding to the C group is detected. The main absorption bands in the IR spectrum are the band caused by vibrations of P=S and P-S bonds included in the fragment (-P) which correspond to 680 cm^{-1} and 650 cm^{-1} . In the PMR spectrum

of O,O-diisopropyl-di-thiophosphoric acid benzyloxymethyl ester, a doublet signal from the $\text{SCH}_2\text{OC}=\text{O}$ group is observed in the region of 5.38 ppm. The nature of the splitting is explained by the spin-spin interaction with the phosphorus nucleus (20 Hz). The $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{C}=\text{O}$ group appears in the weak field region as a multiplet at 7-7.8 ppm. The signals of methyl protons of isopropyl radicals appear at 1.27 ppm, and the signals of methine groups at 4.58 ppm. The spin-spin coupling constant of the C-CH₃ group of the isopropyl radical is 6.47 Hz.

The synthesized esters of the corresponding acids are light yellow liquids, and the esters of DTF acids are light brown.

The physicochemical properties of the synthesized compounds are given in Table 1.

Pic.2. IR and PMR spectra of benzyloxymethylester of diisopropylxanthogenic acid

Table 1

Physico-chemical parameters of compounds

Formula of compounds	Exit %	n_D^{20}	d_4^{20}	MR _D	
				Found	Calculated
$C_6H_5COCH_2SP(OC_3H_7)_2$ C S	85	1,5346	1,1737	92,5	91,8
$C_6H_5COCH_2SP(OC_3H_{11})_2$ C S	86	1,5222	1,1104	111,1	110,3
$C_6H_5COCH_2SCOC_2H_5$ C S	88	1,5820	1,2318	69,3	69,3
$C_6H_5COCH_2SCOC_3H_7$ C S	87	1,5770	1,1911	78,9	74,0
$C_6H_5COCH_2SCOC_4H_9$ C S	87	1,5660	1,1756	78,9	78,5
$C_6H_5COCH_2SCSC_4H_9$ C S	92	1,5940	1,1729	86,83	86,107

The effectiveness of benzoyloxymethyl ethers TTC, KG and DTF as additives was established by testing them in a mixture with MS-20 mineral oil. Extreme pressure properties were studied on a four-ball friction machine (FBM-1) in accordance with GOST 9495-75.

The assessment was made using the scuffing index (Iz), ball welding load (Pc) and jamming load (Pk).

Comparative studies of the compounds we obtained are given in Table 2

Table 2

Test sample	Concentration of compound in oil, %	Friction tests				Tests on the DK-NAMI device				
		Load, N			Wear indicator, mm	Viscosity at 100 ⁰ C, mm ² /c		Viscosity increase, mm ² /s	Sediment %	Corrosion g/cm ²
		Bully in-dex	Jams	welding		Before oxidation	After oxidation			
Масло MC-20	-	303	784	1568	0,62	-	-	-	-	-
$C_6H_5COCH_2SCOC_2H_5$ O S	5,12	509	1097	2890	0,60	16,2	17,0	0,8	0,1	21,0
$C_6H_5COCH_2SCOC_3H_7$ O S	5,40	490	1000	2892	0,50	14,4	18,6	0,9	0,2	27,0
$C_6H_5COCH_2SCOC_4H_9$ O S	5,68	470	980	2469	0,55	17,8	18,8	1,0	0,2	32,0
$C_6H_5COCH_2SCOC_3H_7$ O S	3,99	548	882	3550	0,75	16,1	19,3	3,2	0,3	75,1
$C_6H_5COCH_2SC(OC_3H_7)_2$ O S	6,96	548	1078	2970	0,40	17,6	18,6	1,0	0,1	49,3
$C_6H_5COCH_2SC(OC_3H_{11})_2$ O S	8,08	392	787	2469	0,41	17,7	19,7	2,0	0,1	96,0
$CH_3COCH_2SP(OC_3H_7)_2$ O S	4,83	60	931	3332	0,45	45,6	19,3	3,7	0,2	148,0
$C_6H_5COCH_2SCSC_4H_9$ O S	5,02	548	1236	3685	0,66	16,8	17,5	0,7	0,1	29

Anti-wear properties were also determined on the specified friction machine by measuring the diameter of the wear spot at a constant axial load of 392 N, the rotation speed of the upper ball was 1420 min. Test duration is 1 hour. Thermal-oxidative stability was determined using a DK-NAMI apparatus at a temperature of 140°C for 20 hours in the presence of copper plates 4, while the anti-corrosion properties of the oils were simultaneously determined. The criteria for corrosion were the amount of mass loss of the copper plate (G/cm^3), and the criteria for oxidation were the increase in viscosity and the amount of sediment formed.

In table for comparison, Table 2 shows the test results of benzoyloxymethyl esters of TTC, KG, and DTF acids. All synthesized studies of the compound improve the lubrication properties of mineral oil. Studies have shown the dependence of the lubricating efficiency of compounds on the length of the alkyl radical in xanthogen, trithiocarbamate and dithiophosphorus groups. According to test data, with a change in the length of the alkyl radical in benzoyloxymethyl esters of TTC, KG, and DTF acids, their extreme pressure properties increase: the increase in seizing load is especially noticeable, which, apparently, is explained by the compact adsorption of molecules containing short alkyl radicals; when comparing the test results of esters of CG and DTF acids, it is clear that derivatives of CG acids are inferior in extreme pressure and especially antiwear properties to similar esters of DTF acids, however, in terms of corrosion and viscosity increase surpass them.

Comparative tests of benzoyloxymethyl esters of KG and DTF acids with previously obtained acetoxymethyl esters showed that the replacement of the alkyl radical in the S-alkyl group with a phenyl radical leads to a decrease in the extreme pressure efficiency of these compounds, a particularly noticeable decrease in the welding load and the scuffing index. However, due to the presence of a more polar phenyl group in the composition, benzoyloxymethyl ethers compare favorably with acetoxymethyl esters of KG and DTF acids in their anti-wear, anti-corrosion properties and thermal-oxidative stability.

Thus, the corrosion of copper plates and the increase in viscosity in the case of testing benzoyloxymethyl esters of KG and DTF acids are almost 3 times less and the content of the sediment formed during oxidation is also slightly lower than that of acetoxymethyl ethers.

In addition, benzoyloxymethyl esters of TTC, KG and DTF acids are more thermally stable compared to acetoxymethyl esters. Thermal analysis on a derivator type OD-102 of the F. Paulik, I. Paulik and D. Erden system in a dynamic heating mode at a speed of 5 rpm (Al_2O_3 standard) showed that the temperature range of decomposition of benzoyloxymethyl ester of KG acid corresponds to the 165-305°C temperature range decomposition of acetoxymethyl acid ester – 133-210°C.

Thus, based on benzoyloxymethyl esters of TTC, KG and DTF acids, additives have been obtained with high anti-wear, extreme pressure properties and high thermal stability, which can be used to create effective lubricating oils.

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